

Analysis of Road Safety Strategies in Africa: A Closer Look at the Results through the Moroccan Case Study

Analyse des Stratégies de Sécurité Routière en Afrique : Un Regard Approfondi sur les Résultats à travers l'Étude de Cas du Maroc

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Abstract

Road accidents pose an enduring threat to lives, property, and infrastructure in Africa, challenging countries, societies, and economies despite numerous strategies and governance plans. Alarming and rising accident rates across African nations necessitate preventive actions, including revisiting strategies and fortifying institutional frameworks.

Analyzing this issue involved extracting an African model and examining its strategies, challenges, and stakes. Morocco serves as a case study due to its extensive efforts in attaining road safety, highlighting both successes and failures, alongside existing constraints.

Identifying shortcomings enables proposing initial steps toward ensuring road safety, a pivotal factor in achieving desired outcomes.

Keywords: «accidents; strategies; failures; road safety ».

Résumé

Les accidents routiers persistent comme une menace grave pour la vie, les biens et les infrastructures en Afrique, défiant les pays, les sociétés et les économies malgré les multiples initiatives. Les taux alarmants en croissance continue révèlent l'urgence de revoir les stratégies en place et de renforcer les dispositifs réglementaires pour la prévention. L'analyse se concentre sur un modèle africain, en prenant le Maroc comme étude de cas pour examiner ses efforts, succès, échecs et contraintes en matière de sécurité routière. Identifier les lacunes permettra de formuler des suggestions cruciales pour avancer vers une sécurité routière effective, essentielle pour atteindre les objectifs souhaités.

Mots-Clés : « accidents ; stratégies ; défaillances ; sécurité routière ».

Introduction

In a continent undergoing transition, attraction and emergence, as well as urban growth marked by a rising number of means of road transport, road accidents remain a major concern and a serious development problem that has a considerable impact at all levels, ranking roads among the leading causes of death. Road insecurity leads to human suffering, loss of life and devastating socio-economic consequences for families, societies and governments.

The road safety situation in Africa is very worrying, with the continent's road mortality rate considered the highest in the world. A number of factors, such as economic development, existing infrastructure, available resources and national priorities, can determine the degree to which African countries commit to major road safety projects and strategies. However, some African countries have taken a wide range of steps to tackle road safety problems and have adopted ambitious road safety strategies to reduce casualties and economic losses in response to this scourge, while others have only the name strategy, slogans and banners of reform, but the reality is further from road safety.

Since the 1990s, Morocco, chosen as a model for study, has made considerable efforts, inviting the various stakeholders to participate in this national project through appropriate measures to tackle the harm caused by road accidents and counteract the disastrous consequences of road insecurity. This has given rise to a series of reforms in legislation, regulatory provisions and laws, as well as the upgrading of equipment and logistics. Among the policies initiated in this direction are the adoption of the National Road Safety Strategy for the years 2017-2026 and the creation of the National Road Safety Agency (NARSA) as an agency in charge of road safety in the country.

In this context, it is important to note that Africa does not have enough bodies to constitute a source of real statistics with an initial objective of determining the seriousness of road accidents and identifying challenges and strategic issues, whereas the contribution of road safety stakeholders is based on a scientific analysis of accidentology statistics.

Also, the implementation of road safety strategies often depends on the political will of governments, the financial and technical resources available, and the ability of governments to enforce road safety rules; the scale of the failings and shortcomings raised is revealed by the rising road accident rates recorded in some countries, and indicates that commitments have not been honoured, while some regions face particular challenges such as inadequate

road infrastructure, less stringent safety standards, and economic problems which can hamper the full implementation of road safety initiatives.

To this end, the mobilization of African countries and multilateral institutions, in-depth reflection and an effective response to the problems of road accident trauma, political commitment at all levels: global, African, regional and national, as well as a redoubling of efforts with a strengthening of regulatory and legal provisions and institutional and normative reforms are necessary to minimize the recorded rates of road accidents, given that the lives of millions of Africans depend on the efforts made to guarantee road safety. The scourge of road accidents in Africa calls for a unanimous commitment from all governments, while this issue should be the subject of a mobilization of the various stakeholders to ensure that road safety is among the objectives of sustainable development.

1. The road accident situation

Road accidents are a tragic reality that continues to affect millions of lives worldwide every year. This scourge undermines the sanctity of life, causing devastating trauma and unbearable loss of life, and its consequences, which are not limited to individual suffering, extend to far-reaching socio-economic repercussions.

The studies carried out to analyze the various facets of this problem reveal the alarming scale of road insecurity, and the available data indicate that road accidents represent a major issue affecting all areas of life, from public health to the economy, via social aspects and development. Only the African continent records a road mortality rate estimated at 26.6 per 100,000 inhabitants according to the WHO report, compared with 18.5 in Asia and 10.3 in Europe.

The global annual international cost of these accidents is around 518 billion euros, and the financial impact underlines the gravity of the situation, with economic losses amounting to 1% to 3% of Gross National Product (GNP) in developed countries, and 3% to 5% in developing countries.

1.1. The road accident situation in Africa

From one day to the next, the road safety crisis in Africa continues to worsen at an alarming rate, causing pain and suffering to families, loved ones and societies, as well as having a negative impact on the economies of African countries. These unfortunate consequences do not stop here, but the scourge continues to snatch lives, with the highest class mortality rate in the world, requiring urgent intervention through a willingness to act and a profound treatment

based on an institutional framework inspired by real data and enabling this crisis to be counteracted.

The data presented below by the WHO highlight the alarming road safety situation in Africa:

- African roads are the deadliest in the world, with around 650 people dying every day;
- Half of all road accident fatalities in Africa are among vulnerable road users, such as pedestrians and two- or three-wheeled motorcycles (tricycles) that travel between cities and regions in some African countries;
- Pedestrians represent the highest category of fatalities, followed by motorcyclists and cyclists, in low-income countries; while in middle-income countries, vehicle occupants and pedestrians are most at risk.

According to a report by the World Health Organization (WHO), the world records a rate of 17.4 deaths due to road accidents per 100,000 inhabitants, while Africa records a rate of 26.6 per 100,000 inhabitants. On the other hand, the continent ranks last in terms of motorization, with just 46.6 vehicles per 1,000 people, compared with 510.3 vehicles per 1,000 people in Europe. Africa records a very high number of deaths on its roads about the size of its vehicle fleet. In terms of figures, 2.3% of the world's vehicles are on the road, with 20% of deaths due to traffic accidents, showing that this continent is facing a real road safety crisis. Vulnerable people, or the least protected category of road users, account for half of all fatalities in Africa and include pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists. The meager statistics collected show that 39% of road accident fatalities in Africa are pedestrians and 7% are motorcyclists, while many African countries show a significant influx of motorcycles. These figures do not give a true picture of the road accident situation, as the majority of cases escape detection because African countries do not have data collection centers that meet the required standards, particularly those with low incomes, as well as the absence of detailed fatality data specifying the category of road user.

Data provided by the West African Road Safety Organization show that the income bracket plays a decisive role in the occurrence of a fatal accident on Africa's roads. In low-income countries, where fatal road accident rates are highest at 29.2/100,000 inhabitants, the majority of fatalities are motorcyclists and cyclists, whereas in middle-income countries, where fatal accident rates are recorded at 23.3/100,000 inhabitants, fatalities are vehicle passengers and pedestrians. High-income countries, on the other hand, record a rate of 22.9/100,000 inhabitants.

1.2. The road accident situation in Morocco (case study)

The choice of Morocco to carry out this study on the evaluation of road safety strategies in Africa is based on several criteria:

Morocco is ahead of other African countries in terms of governance and strategic management of the road safety issue, thanks to the best practices it has introduced in this area and its proximity to the European continent, which has enabled it to become a crossroads for the exchange of experience and expertise.

The Kingdom was the first to take the initiative to awaken African awareness of road hazards and the imperative need to adopt effective and efficient strategies in this framework it organized the first African Road Safety Forum under the theme: road safety in Africa, a lever for sustainable development, held between November 13 and 15, 2018 in the city of Marrakech, an event that constitutes a great witness to the efforts made by this country for the concretization of the rules of road safety in the African region ;

In view of the fact that the statistics for recent years cannot give a true picture of the level of road accidents due to the after-effects of the spread of the Coronavirus pandemic and the quarantine of road users during this period, the number of traffic accidents in the Kingdom of Morocco has been high in recent years. According to statistics from the Directorate of Road Transport and Road Safety of the Ministry of Transport and Logistics, 81,827 road accidents were recorded in 2016, compared with 78,864 a year earlier, resulting in 3,593 deaths (up 0.79% on 2015) and 8,950 serious injuries (down 10.11%), while traffic accidents in 2015 were more dangerous than those in 2016.

Despite the increase in the number of traffic accidents in the urban perimeter in 2016 to 58446 accidents compared to the year 2015 of 55847, a slight decrease of 0.15% was recorded in the rate of fatal road accidents from 2613 in 2015 to 2609 in 2016; the rase-compagne also experienced a decrease of 1.68% in road accidents from 23672 road accidents in 2015 to 23281 in 2016.

2. Road safety strategies and plans

Road safety is a major challenge and an issue with an international dimension, requiring the commitment of all the players involved - governments, organizations, authorities, civil society, road users, etc. - given the terrible upward trend in the number of accidents and fatalities. This calls for the mobilization of the various stakeholders to make greater efforts to contain this scourge and counter its unfortunate consequences, through the implementation of new, innovative and creative approaches.

The United Nations has launched the Global Action Programme for Road Safety, which aims to promote road safety worldwide as an international initiative, and many African countries have participated in this initiative and worked to implement appropriate measures to reduce road accidents and improve road user safety.

Similarly, international organizations concerned with road safety are showing a keen interest in minimizing road accidents and creating safer road environments for all users, given that road hazards threaten all countries, especially those in the developing world.

2.1. Road safety strategies in Africa

The integration of all the parameters and factors affecting road traffic has been the primary focus of the comprehensive, multidimensional approach to road safety issues adopted in Africa. At continental level, organizations such as the African Union (AU) and the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) have also put in place programs and strategies to tackle the continent's road safety problems.

In November 2011, the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa organized the second African Road Safety Conference for transport ministers. This meeting enabled the formulation and approval of the action plan for road safety in Africa covering the period 2011 - 2020, which was adopted in January 2012 by the African Heads of State meeting in Luanda, Angola, to enhance road safety management.

In the same vein, a Charter signed by member states with the initial aim of managing road safety, while regional cooperation within this framework was one of the primary objectives of the Economic Community of West African States, within which the West African Road Safety Organization was established.

2.1.1. African Road Safety Plan adopted from 2011 to 2020

The African heads of state meeting in Luanda, Angola, in January 2012 adopted a road safety plan for 2011 - 2020 in Africa based on the satisfaction of five objectives, namely:

- The success of a project, a plan or a program requires the institutionalization of approaches. To this end, road safety management must start with the creation of an institutional framework for the implementation of road safety activities, to guarantee a reference for all measures to be taken;
- The safety of road users, especially the most vulnerable categories such as pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists, requires a high level of mobility and road safety, with the necessary equipment in place;
- Vehicle safety ;

- Extreme concentration must be given to the human factor, which remains the prime culprit in road accidents; actions that must concern behavior and gestures in a psychological reading, training, examinations, driving licenses, enforcement of the highway code, public awareness and education, and the establishment of a road safety culture;

2.1.2. African Road Safety Charter

The initial objective of the African Charter on Road Safety adopted in April 2014 in Malabo, Equatorial Guinea, at the third session of the Conference of African Ministers of Transport, hinges on reducing the number of fatal road accidents by 50% by 2020 and strengthening road safety in Africa through a policy framework enabling contribution in road safety and harmonization of road safety data by stimulating road safety strategies at national level enabling the development of road safety programs.

2.1.3. Cooperation on road safety

When it comes to road safety, Africa has seen several forms of collaboration:

First and foremost, the improvement of road safety, which contributes to the quality of life of the continent's inhabitants, was considered a pioneering objective of the African Development Community's 2001 Protocol, an objective that cannot be achieved without the establishment of an institutional framework and harmonization of regulatory provisions relating to vehicle and driver safety, as well as the introduction of a regional traffic management plan.

Secondly, monitoring and support through awareness-raising campaigns, ongoing research into effective solutions for minimizing accident rates in African countries, and the transfer of knowledge and technology in this field.

Thirdly, the key role played by the West African Road Safety Organization as a regional model for knowledge exchange, with its own initiatives such as the ongoing sharing of ideas aimed at strengthening road safety management capacity in the region.

Lastly, capitalizing on the achievements of international organizations specializing in the road safety sector and the contribution of African partners through the experience and expertise of each other to ensure that the initial objectives and key success factors are the socio-economic and cultural relationships between these African countries.

These organizations include the World Health Organization (WHO), the Fédération Internationale de l'Automobile (FIA), the International Transport Forum (ITF), the Fédération Routière Internationale (FRT), the World Bank (WB) and the African Development Bank (ADB), etc....

2.2. Road safety strategies in Morocco

The implementation of a road safety management framework in Africa relies on the existence of solid governance models within its states. Morocco, inspired by this desire and a member of the African Road Safety Charter, has made considerable efforts in terms of governance and strategic management of road safety in order to stop the hemorrhaging and reduce the accident rate recorded on the country's roads.

The Kingdom of Morocco has responded to international efforts in this area by introducing an arsenal of institutional and regulatory reforms tailored to road accidents, which have terrible consequences for health and the economy. Over the years, it has initiated plans, strategies and reforms that concern all its regions without discrimination, to act effectively on the resurgence of accidents, while fully addressing the factors responsible for road traffic, through the determination of the population affected by this scourge.

Public decision-makers have initiated actions aimed at reducing the frequency of road accidents and have given high priority to road safety issues. To combat road insecurity, the actions initiated focus on introducing normative and institutional reforms and improving road safety governance.

In this climate, the new road safety strategy 2016 - 2025 was born and developed with an initial target of reducing the number of road deaths by 25% in 2020 and 50% by 2025.

In the same vein, and among the measures that have been taken, we are talking about the implementation of the points-based driving license, which is considered to be a fair, educational and non-discriminatory system insofar as it is applied to all drivers, whatever their standard of living or professional category. This is an additional means of sanctioning road safety, the principle of which consists of allocating each driver a capital of points that can be reduced, starting with an initial capital of points that is lost as and when offenses are committed.

According to the Moroccan Highway Code, during the two (2)-year trial period, all drivers have a capital of twenty (20) points when they obtain their driving license, then when it becomes permanent, the capital increases to thirty (30) points. If the driver does not commit an offence punishable by the loss of points for 3 years, he or she recovers the full balance, i.e. all 30 points. The Ministry of Transport and Logistics is responsible for the regulation and administration of transport, including the withdrawal of points from driving licenses following the discovery of a traffic offence by enforcement officers punishable by the withdrawal of points or a final court decision.

In the same vein, if the driver attends a road safety education session or does not commit any offence punishable by the withdrawal of points for one year, the Road Transport Department under the aforementioned Ministry credits the driver's driving license balance with four points. If, on the other hand, the driver has a balance of less than 8 points and has not committed an offence punishable by the withdrawal of points for 2 years, the balance is increased to 12 points.

The Highway Code provides for the possibility of deducting points from the driving license of any driver at fault, and sometimes withdrawing them if the rules of the road are not observed. In a spirit of adjustment, the holder of the driving license can recover lost points and make up for them if he observes certain rules, the driver can follow road safety education sessions, which enable him not only to recover a few points, but also to improve his behavior and consequently preserve his life and that of other users of the public highway.

The Highway Code was designed and adopted as part of the national integrated road safety strategy, which was drawn up in 2002, finalized in 2003 and came into force in April 2004. It was implemented through a series of action plans at three-yearly intervals, known as Integrated Emergency Strategic Plans (IESPs).

The first plan covers the period from 2004 to 2006, the second from 2008 to 2010 and the third from 2011 to 2013. The evaluation of these plans is being carried out with the assistance of the World Bank, in perfect coordination with all the players involved in road safety at national level.

The Highway Code was adopted as part of an integrated vision aimed at modernizing the country's legal arsenal relating to road safety. In addition, a number of regulatory provisions were introduced even before the Highway Code was adopted, such as the decree requiring seatbelts to be worn on front seats in urban areas, and the requirement for heavy goods vehicles to carry certain road safety equipment.

Law 52-05 was a necessity, insofar as the previous law dated back to 1953. The new highway code offered a modern platform, in line with the country's socio-economic changes and technological advances, and also brought the company up to date with international regulations.

Morocco has adopted a new strategy based on resolution 64/255 of the United Nations General Assembly, with the aim of stagnating and then minimizing the number of road accident victims. This 10-year strategy covers the period from 2017 to 2026, and capitalizes on the achievements of international organizations specializing in road safety. This strategy

has taken into account the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) relating to road safety, which aim to reduce the number of victims and injuries in road accidents by half, following the example of the European experience, which targets a reduction in the number of road accident victims to 50% by 2020, compared with 2010 figures.

The pillars of this Integrated National Road Safety Strategy 2017 - 2026 are based on 5 essential pillars, in line with the Decade of Action for Road Safety 2011 - 2020, as well as on the results of national traffic accident statistics over the last 10 years.

The strategy identified 5 strategic issues and targets:

- Good management of road safety issues;
- Reaching the safest routes;
- The use of safer vehicles;
- Education and training, communication and awareness-raising, and enforcement will all help to ensure safer road users;
- Post-accident assistance.

In a press release issued on 25/02/2022 by the Ministry in charge of the sector, former Moroccan Transport Minister Aziz Rebbah stated that the integrated national strategy is based on the overhaul of road safety legislation, the reform of driving test systems and the adaptation of roadways and infrastructures, driver training, the strengthening of enforcement and the monitoring of sanctions. A strategy which explains the importance of road safety management, and which has been put in place by Morocco's Department of Transport.

Among the main achievements of this strategy are the institutionalization of the inter-ministerial road safety committee chaired by the Head of Government, the adoption of a new highway code and the upgrading of the road network and equipment.

2.2.1. Road Safety Plans adopted in Morocco :

The Kingdom of Morocco has a long history in the field of road safety. Since 1977, it has initiated a panoply of measures concerning all regions and provinces, aimed at reducing the number of road accidents recorded and reflecting the public policies adopted, hence the creation of a commission reporting to the Ministry of Transport, the first in the field of road safety.

To comply with international recommendations on road safety, the Moroccan government has adopted a new strategy covering the period 2017 - 2026, based on the evaluation of actions planned under the Integrated Strategic Emergency Plan initiated between 2003 and 2013.

❖ **Integrated Strategic Emergency Plan (PSIU) 2003 - 2013**

Following the rise in the number of vehicles, the extension of the road network and the annual increase in the number of fatalities to an average of 4.8% during the period 1996-2003, Moroccan decision-makers implemented an integrated strategic plan to counteract the scourge of road accidents and act on related issues.

To this end, at the meeting of the Interministerial Road Safety Committee on November 3, 2003, the government adopted a 10-year Integrated National Strategy aimed at reducing the number of people killed and seriously injured each year, effectively coordinating planned actions involving legislation, enforcement, penalties, education and information, in order to act on risk factors, and promoting new road safety governance based on consultation and harmonization of the objectives of institutional players.

A strategy spread over three three-year plans: PSIU I, PSIU II and PSIU III, with actions evolving since the initiation of the first phase.

❖ **Integrated Strategic Emergency Plan I (2004-2006):**

The Integrated Strategic Emergency Road Safety Program has been adopted to curb the number of road fatalities and counteract the causes of accidents, with seven priority areas recommended by the National Strategy:

- Legislation;
- Education;
- Communication;
- Reform of the driving test system ;
- Driver training and continuing education;
- Urban roadways and infrastructures;
- High-level road safety coordination and management;
- Rescue services for victims of traffic accidents.

To better support the actions planned under these headings, and for greater effectiveness and efficiency, the designers of the first phase of the PSIU have implemented action plans to achieve the desired objectives.

❖ **Integrated Strategic Emergency Plan II (2008 - 2010) :**

In a process of continuity and consolidation of achievements, the 3-year Integrated Strategic Emergency Plan II (2008 - 2010) has been implemented to reinforce the seven priorities set by PSIU 1 in terms of implementation of actions already started but not yet completed, coordination and control, and integration of new structuring actions expected to have a definite impact on improving road safety.

2.2.2. The National Road Control Plan (PNCR) :

Three control plans were thus implemented to accompany and reinforce the various phases of the PSIU, namely: PNCR I, PNCR II, and PNCR III; these actions projected by the road safety stakeholders to concretize the orientations envisaged by the national road control plan, hence the PNCR was elaborated with the objective of :

- Coordinate enforcement action to promote road safety;
- Optimize the use of checking fixtures ;
- Standardize control procedures ;
- Ensure healthy and fair conditions of competition between transport companies.
- The National Road Safety Strategy 2017 - 2026.

Despite the many actions and operations carried out during the decade 2003 - 2013, the scourge of road insecurity continues to weigh heavily on the economy and health, which explains why it can never be eradicated.

To this end, public decision-makers intend to extend the actions to combat road accidents through a new strategy covering the period 2017 - 2026 and divided into two phases: 2017 - 2021 and 2022 - 2026.

The aim of this new strategy is to develop responsible behavior and safer roads in Morocco. It sets a target of halving the number of road deaths by 2026 from its current level (fewer than 1,900 road deaths by 2026).

❖ **National, regional and local stakeholders**

Road safety is a major undertaking that concerns all sectors, as the roads continue to claim victims in a merciless war fueled by a number of factors, such as driver behavior, the decisions of pedestrians and users, the quality of road infrastructure and vehicle condition. But the strong point of road safety management in Morocco is the close collaboration between all the players involved.

❖ National Road Safety Agency (NARSA).

The Agence Nationale de la Sécurité Routière (National Road Of Security Agency) under the acronym "NARSA" is a public establishment created on March 12, 2018 under the supervision of the Ministry of Transport and Logistics, enjoying legal personality and financial autonomy, replacing the Comité National de Prévention des Accidents de la Circulation created by decree n°2-72-275 on 15/07/1977 in the form of a public utility establishment. The agency aims to become Morocco's leading road safety organization, with an international reach.

The agency's resources are ensured by subsidies from the State, public and private bodies, and parafiscal taxes set up for its benefit:

- Study and propose to the competent authorities appropriate measures to reduce the number of traffic accidents;

- Bringing local authorities closer to citizens, especially road users,
- To help educate the public by all means, especially through information;
- Promoting responsible road behaviour;
- Make material resources available to road safety departments.

- Improve road safety and the quality of services provided to road users through the various missions it has been assigned to promote road safety.

Since its creation, NARSA has contributed through the various road safety campaigns it has organized to raising user awareness of the dangers of the road and non-compliance with the provisions of the highway code. NARSA participates in the popularization of road safety education, and is actively involved in the activities scheduled for the national road safety day, choosing a theme each year to celebrate the event. The theme is in line with the concerns of public decision-makers in the field of road safety. In 2017, for example, the theme chosen was: "In open country, let's be vigilant". The reasons that prompted the ex-Committee to opt for this theme were justified by the scale of accidents in rural areas. Indeed, "according to national statistics, two-thirds of those killed in traffic accidents in Morocco lose their lives in rural areas. It is to raise public awareness of this alarming figure that the National Road Safety Agency (NARSA) is highlighting the dangers of driving outside built-up areas in 2021. Indeed, driving outside the urban perimeter requires greater vigilance and attention because of the road risks due essentially to speeding, faulty overtaking, slipping and fatigue and drowsiness on the fly".

As part of its activities, the agency has carried out a number of road safety initiatives. These include organization of the national competition for the best school project, organization of seminars on road safety education, collaboration with regional education and training academies, organization of regional seminars on road safety, organization of areas dedicated to road safety education as part of vacation camps organized by the Ministry of Youth and Sports; developing, building and equipping mini-circuits under partnership agreements with local authorities; producing road safety education guides targeting different road users, etc.

The Agency often projects its actions within a partnership framework, by associating public players and associations. Indeed, to mark its contribution, NARSA has used famous slogans during its awareness campaigns, such as: "Let's change the way we drive" and "Your safety is our priority", to live up to the aspirations of a modern society where the values of responsibility and civic-mindedness take precedence over individual recklessness.

With the publication of the latest World Report on Road Safety by the World Health Organization (WHO), NARSA has become a key player in the road safety arena, not only at regional and national level, but also at international level, and this is the fruit of wide-ranging consultation with all the players concerned, especially those involved in enforcement.

3. analysis of results

The public plans and policies implemented and the prevention and safety rules introduced within this framework are proving insufficient to act effectively on road use and attenuate the curve of road accidents despite the efforts deployed by the various players in this field. The number of victims is rising sharply, and the continuing insecurity continues to haunt road users, generating a climate of collective stress and anxiety. This problem threatens all levels of society, the economy and public order, and calls for public action to make the roads safer. Improving road safety requires restructuring the institutional framework to pacify social and economic security.

The latest annual report from the World Health Organization (WHO), which monitors road safety on an international scale, shows that road accident fatalities fell by 30% between 2000 and 2020 in high-income countries. However, this downward trend has not been observed in African countries, where the number of victims continues to rise. It should be noted that more than half of the people who die as a result of these accidents are young adults aged between 15 and 44, the majority of them male. Sadly, these are often people who form an essential pillar of support within their families.

According to WHO criteria, only seven Western countries have comprehensive road safety legislation, while some 80 countries, the majority of which are in Africa, have yet to develop a national strategy to combat road insecurity.

4. suggestions

African countries and multilateral institutions need to mobilize and collaborate with international organizations to share best practices, coordinate efforts and provide an effective response to the problems of road traffic injuries and to improve road safety by strengthening regulatory and legal provisions and institutional and normative reforms to minimize road accident rates.

First and foremost, the lessons learned from international road safety plans need to be exploited, as road safety has prompted multilateral organizations, donor countries and finance ministries to mobilize financially and commit politically to an effective response to the issue. For some countries, this explicitly recognized burden has become an objective of sustainable development at all levels, including the economy and sustainable transport.

With a view to minimizing the number of road accidents, international organizations must scrupulously supervise and carry out appropriate studies on road risk prevention measures, and issue relevant recommendations to the various players involved, in order to improve and promote road safety policies and restore confidence to African road users; the fruits of these efforts, the accumulated experience, guidelines and recommendations issued by specialists in the field must be exploited, especially in those countries that suffer most from this scourge, such as the African continent, so that the prevention of road accidents, the protection of road users and the reduction of road traffic-related injuries and deaths are among the objectives to be achieved.

In this vein, the overriding aim of international efforts is to support individual countries in the establishment of institutional governance aimed at supervising, organizing and sustainably developing the conditions required to achieve an advanced level of road safety. Experience has shown that the combination of funding a governing body, implementing a well thought-out and planned system, and setting targets are all necessary for sustainable action in the field of road safety.

At international level, the Decade of Action for Road Safety 2011-2020 has tried to converge actions and set the expected objectives in terms of road safety through a panoply of measures, namely:

- Governments must put in place the laws and regulations needed to promote road safety, as a matter of the utmost priority. These include overhauling legislation, training drivers, providing psychological support for road users, stepping up enforcement and adapting penalties, reforming driving test systems, and redesigning road and highway infrastructure in line with international regulations; These changes will opt for speed limits, compliance with driving codes and rules, criminalization of certain acts of driving such as driving without a license, lack of insurance....., as well as measures to crack down on dangerous behaviour and actions such as drink-driving and distracted driving.
- Strict enforcement of traffic laws to deter dangerous behavior on the road. This involves speed checks, alcohol tests, fines and penalties for traffic offences.
- Check, monitor and ensure the condition of road infrastructure, which must contribute to accident reduction through the design of roads, bridges and tunnels, the installation of clear and effective road signs and the creation of bicycle paths and sidewalks for pedestrians.
- The use of Automotive Technology, given that technological advances in vehicles can also help to improve road safety. For example, driver assistance systems such as automatic emergency braking, lane departure warning and adaptive cruise control can help prevent accidents.
- Road safety awareness is crucial to reducing accidents. Awareness campaigns focusing on road safety can help promote good driving practices among cab drivers and reduce the number of accidents.
- Road safety education programs can include driving lessons, awareness campaigns on the dangers of reckless driving, the use of seatbelts and child restraints, and information on the risks associated with drinking and driving, as these programs play an essential role in accident prevention.
- Road users, especially the vulnerable category, need to be aware of the risks on the road and of the behaviors and actions undertaken on the road. To this end, road user awareness campaigns are essential, as are specific training and actions, and ongoing monitoring.

In 2010, the United Nations General Assembly adopted a 10-year resolution (2010-2020) on road safety, with the aim of stabilizing and then reducing the number of road accident fatalities worldwide. The resolution calls on Member States to carry out road safety activities

in the areas of road management, road user behavior, training, infrastructure and care for road accident victims.

The actions undertaken by international organizations and bodies highlight the leading role played by the World Health Organization (WHO) in guiding these efforts, working in partnership with national and international stakeholders to provide multi-sectoral assistance to all countries in the planning, implementation and evaluation of road safety policies, to advocate road safety at the highest political level by compiling and disseminating best practice in prevention, data collection and casualty care, by communicating information on risks and ways to reduce them to the general public through annual reports, and by emphasizing the need for increased funding.

In 2017, WHO had published the international *Save Lives* campaign, to provide guidance to member states on road safety to halve the total number of deaths and injuries from road crashes. This technical module focused on vehicle safety management, road law enforcement, infrastructure design and user awareness.

In this sense, the plan for the decade of action for road safety calls for the introduction of an integrated system aimed at minimizing the consequences of accidents through the interaction of all elements related to road traffic, i.e. road users, networks, vehicles and the road environment.

The Plan for the Decade of Action was underpinned by guiding principles tending towards a safe road transport system that takes account of the vulnerability of the human body and is better adapted to human error. Human error must be accepted, tolerated and studied in order to understand that road accidents are not completely avoidable, that a safe system will prevent accidents leading to serious trauma, and that the road environment and vehicles must be in full harmony.

Finally, road users, vehicles, the road network and the road environment as risk factors need to be considered in an integrated way as part of a wide range of interventions, while more emphasis needs to be placed on the analysis of these factors than on traditional road safety approaches.

So for Morocco, taken as a case study of African reality, a number of actions affecting public policy stakeholders in Morocco have been suggested to anticipate and participate in this major road safety project, knowing that most sectors are concerned by this scourge, namely :

1. Ministry of Habouss and Islamic Affairs Morocco is a Muslim country, so speeches at the AL Jomouaa prayer, for example, as well as religious gatherings and meetings, must all

contribute to raising people's awareness of road risks and the need to respect the sacredness of life. This awareness must not be limited to the commemoration of Road Safety Day. People who have been made aware of these rules should be encouraged to pass them on to their families and friends.

2. Ministry of Transport and Logistics Setting up training and awareness programs on modern technologies in the transport sector, particularly for drivers, to improve their driving skills
3. The Ministry of Equipment and Water Roads should be equipped with entertainment and relaxation areas, as well as Motels with preferential prices, as in European countries, to give road users a rest. These areas should also be equipped with sanitary blocks. road signs reserved for professionals to avoid sudden stops and encourage passengers to gather in a specific area such as
4. of National Education, Preschool and Sports

Ministry of Higher Education, Scientific Research and Innovation The integration of road safety disciplines and courses into school curricula and teaching programs for students, given that the Integrated Strategic Emergency Plan III (2011-2013) has initiated road safety education, scientific research, and technological monitoring (understanding the causes of accidents; influence of alcohol, drugs and narcotics consumption; automated control of technical overload and citizen behavior) among its main thrusts.

These courses can be a preliminary preparation and introduction to road use training and should be compulsory core subjects for all levels of education.

For higher education, study the possibility of integrating specialties, subsidiaries, and modules containing accidentology-related training and enabling more in-depth studies of road accidents and the sciences involved.

It should also be pointed out that developing countries do not have schools and institutes specializing in transport and road safety, as developed countries do. This calls for reflection and the mobilization of the sectors concerned to create schools and institutes specializing in this field, enabling them to contribute to the treatment of the scourge, rationalize the expenditure due, have specialists and skills in road safety and at the same time create jobs that can also participate in this major project.

The Ministry can also organize competitions within this framework. The role of these competitions is to define and identify road hazards, and to mobilize all sections of society to play their part in reducing accident rates.

Encouraging people to take part in sports remains one of the most important and effective initial remedies for various forms of suffering, problems, nervousness and stress among road users, especially professionals.

5. Ministry of Economy and Finance Upstream: study the possibility of adding to the headings specifically earmarked for road safety, and increasing the volume of appropriations granted to the departments concerned in the Finance bills, to help minimize accident rates; this vision can be achieved in the short, medium and long term. Downstream: increase the amount of transactional and lump-sum fines paid by offenders, so that they are not just a loss for the economy, but also a source of revenue. Provide local authorities with a budget line dedicated to road safety, as set out in the Integrated Emergency Strategic Plan III (2011-2013).
6. Ministry of Justice The law remains the principal means of intervention in road safety, despite the vital role played by education and prevention. For this reason, it would be desirable to strengthen the existing legal arsenal by studying the implementation of a series of laws capable of minimizing the rate of road accidents, which have a direct impact on the economy and health. In terms of comparative law, simplified procedures are needed to ensure that the control and sanction system operates efficiently. European companies have categorically rejected this high level of road insecurity. To this end, the amount of compensation awarded by the courts has risen sharply in recent years as one of several preventive measures.
7. Ministry of Health and Social Protection drivers are a target for a number of illnesses, such as TMS (musculoskeletal disorders) due to continuous vibrations on the spine, burnout, fatigue at work, haemorrhoids, etc. To this end, it is essential to integrate certain measures that can guarantee better driving conditions, especially for professionals, through more comfortable driving seats,
8. Ministère de l'Aménagement du territoire National, de l'Urbanisme, de l'Habitat et de la Politique de la Ville (Ministry of National Planning, Urban Development, Housing and Urban Policy) Provide dedicated stop-off points for public transit vehicles, similar to bus stations, Reinforce the signposting system, particularly in companion plantations Integrate new technology into the public transport sector.
9. Ministry of Tourism, Crafts and the Social Solidarity Economy A country's road accident rate is a key indicator of the tourism sector and tourist safety. To this end, the Ministry can participate in this project by inviting the various components to take part in

this awareness-raising campaign (posters and banners at borders, hotels, public places and tourist areas encouraging people to obey the highway code, vignettes and videos designed to encourage tourism should also highlight the efforts made and the road safety programs).

10. Ministry of Energy Transition and Sustainable Development Use of greener vehicles that can incorporate green energy and help protect the environment,

11. Ministry of Youth, Culture and Communication Awareness-raising campaigns and the reinforcement of television programs and advertisements that incorporate rigor, respect for others and the highway code by all users.

Conclusion:

By way of conclusion, our article highlights the urgent need for a response to the worrying situation of road insecurity in Africa, characterized by alarming rates of mortality on the roads. The managerial and scientific implications of this study are crucial to the formulation of appropriate strategies.

From a managerial point of view, governments and stakeholders must be fully committed to implementing tangible measures. This requires strong political will, adequate financial and technical resources, and the ability to enforce road safety rules. Managers and decision-makers must also work to strengthen institutional and regulatory standards to bring about significant changes in road safety.

In scientific terms, this research highlights the need for an in-depth analysis of the underlying factors contributing to road accidents in Africa. In-depth studies of road infrastructure, safety standards, economics, and other socio-economic aspects are essential to inform the design and implementation of effective policies. In addition, ongoing research and up-to-date data are needed to assess the effectiveness of measures taken and adjust strategies in line with the results.

In focusing on prospects, it is crucial to recognize current limitations and persistent challenges. Gaps in road infrastructure, inadequate safety standards, and economic difficulties hamper the full implementation of road safety initiatives. These challenges require a proactive approach to achieve significant progress.

Finally, the main contribution of our research lies in the need for collective mobilization at all levels, from governments to stakeholders, to integrate road safety as a key objective of sustainable development in Africa. This requires coordinated action, heightened awareness and shared responsibility to tackle this crisis. It highlights the urgent need for immediate, coordinated action to reverse the current trend in road accidents in Africa. It calls for collective mobilization, strengthened institutional and normative reforms, and continued vigilance to ensure that road safety remains at the heart of the continent's sustainable development goals.

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